
A Study on Purposes and Patterns of Social Media Use among College Students

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Abstract Social media plays a vital role of college students' daily lives, influencing their communication, learning, and social interactions. In recent era, social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, TikTok, YouTube, Twitter, Flicker and Telegram have gained immense popularity among college students. These platforms have transformed the way students communicate, access information, and engage in learning activities. Nowadays, our daily life is fundamentally based on social media. If we want to buy or sell something, we take the help of social media. It has become an essential part of our lives. It plays a significant role in education by facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing, and online learning. This research paper aims to analyze the key purposes and motivations behind social media use among college students. A descriptive survey method was adopted, and data was collected from college students using a structured questionnaire. The findings reveal that students primarily use social media for communication, entertainment, academic support, and staying informed. The study highlights both educational and social purposes of social media usage.

Keywords: Social media, college students, communication,

Introduction

The rapid advancement in digital technology has significantly transformed the way of individual's communication, interaction and access to information. Among these technological innovations, social media platforms have become an integral part of daily life, particularly for college students. Social media refers to web-based applications that enable users to create, share, and exchange content within virtual communities and networks (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, X (formerly Twitter) and Snapchat are widely used by students for various academic, social, and recreational purposes. Social media is an online platform that allows users to create content, connect with others, seek entertainment, and share information. It creates a space where anyone can build networks form online communities for socialization, and information exchange. An online platform where users can share information and connect with virtual communities through text, videos, photos, and other content is called social media.

. Social media creates virtual spaces that allow users to interact with each other without any geographical boundaries. Youth of colleges represent one of the most active demographic groups on social media due to their high levels of internet accessibility, technological literacy and social connectivity. Easy access to smart phones and the internet further contributes to their extensive use of social media. Understanding the purposes of social

media use among college students is important for educators and institutions to effectively integrate these platforms into the teaching–learning process. Previous studies indicate that students use social media not only for social interaction and entertainment but also for educational activities, information seeking, professional networking, and self-expression (Junco, 2012). The integration of social media into students' daily life has reshaped learning environments, peer relationships and communication patterns within higher education institutions. As per the Data Reported of Global Social Media Statistics in 2025 social media had more than five billion global users, which is equal to more than 68% of the world population (Global Social Media Statistics). It offers numerous benefits, including enhanced collaboration, knowledge sharing and social support. Excessive or inappropriate use has also been associated with negative outcomes such as distraction, reduced academic performance, anxiety and addiction (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). Understanding the specific purposes and patterns for which college students use social media is therefore essential for educators, policymakers and mental health professionals to maximize its positive potential and on the other hand minimizing its adverse effects.

This study aims to examine the various purposes and patterns of social media usage among college students of Sirmour district of Himachal Pradesh, including academic, social, entertainment, and personal development motivations. By analyzing students' usage patterns and underlying intentions, the research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of how social media influences student life and academic experiences in contemporary higher education settings.

Need for the Study: This research paper will help educators to guide the students toward positive and educational use of social media. This study is essential to understand how social media is utilized by college students of Sirmour district of Himachal Pradesh and how it can be better used for educational development. This study will help the parents of college students to understand the impact of social media.

Objectives of the Study: The main objectives of the research paper are as follows:

1. To identify the main purposes and patterns of social media usage among college students.
2. To analyze the educational purposes of social media usage.
3. To study the social and entertainment-related purposes of social media usage.

Methodology: The study adopted a descriptive survey method. This method is used to describe the behavior pattern of college students about the usage of social media.

- **Sample:** The sample consisted of 120 college students of Sirmour district selected using simple random sampling.
- **Tool:** A structured online questionnaire was developed based on various purposes of social media usage, including communication, education, entertainment, and personal development.
- **Data Analysis:** The collected data were analyzed using simple percentage analysis.
- **Data Analysis and Findings of the Study:** In this study only 120 college students of Sirmour district of Himachal Pradesh participated and filled an online questionnaire. 66 are female and 54 are male. The demographical profile of the respondents is given in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic profile of respondents.

Characteristics	Distribution	Respondents (N)	Percentage (%)
Subjects		120	100 %
Age (in years)	18-20	116	96.7%
	21-23	3	2.5%
	23-25	Nil	0%
	above 25	1	0.8%
Gender	Male	54	45%
	Female	66	55%
Region	Rural	100	83.3%
	Urban	20	16.7%
Classes	Ist year	69	57.5%
	2nd year	36	30%
	3rd year	15	12.5%

Streams	Arts	89	74.2%
	Medical	5	4.2%
	Non-Medical	9	7.5%
	Commerce	11	9.1%
	B.Voc	3	2.5%
	BCA	3	2.5%
Hostel Facility	Yes	59	49.2%
	No	61	50.8%

From table 1 it is clear that 45 percent respondents (N=54) are male and 55 percent respondents (N=66) are female of different age groups. Out of the total samples, 96.7 percent samples (N= 116) are between the age group of 18-20 years, 2.5 percent samples (N= 3) are between the age group of 21-23 years, no one between the age group of 23-25 years and only 0.8 percent (N=1) are above the age 25 years . From table it is observed that 83.3 percent samples (N=100) belong from rural area, and 16.7 percent samples (N=20) belong from urban area. The educational status of the samples is also described in table 1. From table, it is clear that 57.5 percent (N=69) respondents are first year students, 30 percent (N=36) respondents are second year students, 12.5 percent (N=15) respondents are final year students. . All the respondents have specified their educational status. The age wise distribution of the respondents from the sample is shown in figure 1. From the variation, it is clear that 96.7 percent samples (N= 116) are between the age group of 18-20 years, 2.5 percent samples (N= 3) are between the age group of 21-23 years, no one between the age group of 23-25 years and only 0.8 percent (N=1) are above the age 25 years.

Figure 1: Age Wise Distribution of respondents.

Figure 2: Streams Wise Distribution

The streams wise status of the respondents is shown in figure 2. From this distribution, it is clear that 74.2 percent respondents (N=89) belongs from arts stream, 4.2 percent (N=5) respondents belongs from B.Sc. medical, 7.5 percent (N=9) belongs from B.Sc non medical, 9.1 percent (N=11) respondents from commerce, 2.5 percent (N=3) respondents from vocational subject and 2.5 percent (N=3) respondents belongs from BCA.

Status regarding hostel facilities of the respondents is shown in figure 3. From figure, it is observed that 49.2 percent (N=59) respondents are hostel residents and 50.8 percent (N=61) respondents are staying outside.

Figure 3: Hostel Avilaing by Respondents

The distribution of the use of devices is reported in table 2. From table, it is clear that the all the respondents have smart phones. On the other hand, 94.3 percent have only Smartphone as e- gadget, 0.8 percent have computer as a e- gadget, 3.3 percent have both smart phone and computer as a e- gadget, 0.8 percent have smart phone, computer tablet and notepad and 0.8 percent have tablet. The findings indicates that 58.3 percent of respondents access social media using mobile data while 4.2 percent of respondents use Wi-Fi to access social media. On the other hand 37.5 percent respondents use both connection such as mobile data and Wi-Fi to connect social media platforms. Variation of the use of e-gadgets such as smartphone, computer, notepad or tablets and data connectivity is shown in figure 4, which concludes that most of the respondents use their mobile data to access social media.

Table 2: Distribution of scores about the use of smart phones and data uses.

Characteristics	Distribution	Respondents (N)	Percentage %
Smart Phones	Yes	120	100%
	No	Nil	0%
Type of e-gazettes	Smartphone	113	94.3%
	Computer	1	0.8%
	Smartphone, Computer	4	3.3%
	Smartphone, Computer, Tablet, Notepad etc	1	0.8%
	Tablet	1	0.8%
Data Use	Moblie Data	70	58.3%
	Wi-fi Data	5	4.2%
	Both	45	37.5%

Figure 4: Variation about the use of the smartphones and data uses.

The distribution of scores about the use of Social Media and time spend for various purposes and patterns are shown in table 3. The results indicate a significant difference in social media account ownership among the respondents. In the case of account on social media is found that 96.7 percent (N=116) have their account on different social media only 3.3 respondents using social media with out their account. So most of the repondents have an account on different social media platforms. These results are also shown in figure 5 related accounts on social media platforms.

Table 3: Distribution of scores about the use of Social Media and time spend for various purposes.

Characteristics	Distribution	Respondents (N)	Percentage (%)
Accounts on Social Media	Yes	116	96.7 %
	No	4	3.3%
Average hours Spend on Smart Phones or on digital device during last one year	Less than 1 hour	11	9.2%
	1-2 Hours	42	35%
	2-4 hours	51	42.5%
	6-8 Hours	13	10.8%
	more Than 8 Hours	3	2.5%
Time Spend on Social Media in a day	Less than 1 hour	14	11.7%
	1-2 Hours	54	45%
	2-4 hours	43	35.8%
	4-6 Hours	7	5.8%
	more Than 6 Hours	2	1.7%
Time period	Early Morning	6	5%
	Morning	15	12.5%
	Afternoon	26	21.7%
	Evening	55	45.8%
Purpose	Late Night	18	15%
	Communication	62	51.7%
	Education	18	15%
	Entertainment	36	30%
	News/ Information	4	3.3%

Figure 5: Distribution about accounts on social media

From table 3 it is clear that the majority of the respondents spend a considerable amount of time on smart phones or other digital devices. Specifically, 42.5 percent (N=51) of respondents using digital devices for 2–4 hours in a day, followed by 35 percent (N=42) respondents usage of 1–2 hours daily. A smaller proportion of respondents (10.8%) reported spending 6–8 hours per day on digital devices. In contrast, 9.2 percent of respondents reported using digital devices for less than one hour per day, while only 2.5 percent indicated usage of more than eight hours per day. The findings indicate that most respondents spend a moderate amount of time on social media each day. Nearly half of the respondents 45percent reported spending 1–2 hours daily on social media, while 35.8% indicated spending 2–4 hours per day. A smaller proportion of respondents reported lower or higher usage levels 11.7% spent less than one hour per day on social media, 5.8% spent 4–6 hours, and only 1.7% reported spending more than six hours daily.

Regarding the preferred time period for social media use, the majority of respondents (45.8%) reported using social media most frequently in the evening. This was followed by the afternoon (21.7%) and late night (15%). Few of the respondents reported using social media in the morning (12.5%) or early morning (5%) and variation is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Distribution about time spend and time period on social media.

The results reported in table 3 indicate that there is a significant difference between the uses of different social media platforms. The distribution of purposes indicates that communication is the predominant use, accounting for 51.7% of the total. Entertainment represents the second most common purpose at 30%, followed by education at 15%. In contrast, news and information seeking constitutes a relatively small proportion at 3.3%.

Figure 7: Distribution about purposes behind the use of social media.

Overall, the data suggest that functional and social interaction needs outweigh informational purposes among respondents. Figure 7 presents the distribution of different purposes underlying social media use.

Conclusion

This study confirms that social media plays a vital role among college students, serving multiple purposes such as communication, information seeking, entertainment, academic collaboration, self-expression and career development. While it offers numerous benefits, responsible and balanced use is essential to maximize its positive impact. This study concludes that social media, when used wisely, can be a powerful educational resource for college students. The findings suggest that social media can be effectively used as an educational tool if guided properly. Teachers can use social media platforms to share learning materials, conduct discussions, and encourage collaborative learning. Institutions should also educate students about time management and responsible usage of social media. Hence, we can conclude that most college students use social media daily. Communication and entertainment are the primary purposes of social media usage. A significant number of students use social media for academic activities such as sharing notes, attending online classes, and discussing assignments. Students also use social media for staying informed about current events and career opportunities. Excessive use for entertainment was reported by some students, which may affect academic focus.

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